

ONLINE GAME-BASED STRATEGY IN TEACHING ARLING PANLIPUNAN AND THE STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to find out the relationship of using game-based learning in terms of Rules, Immersive, Enjoyment, Multimedia Technology, and Challenge and Competition to the academic performance of Grade 8 students in Araling Panlipunan, specifically in terms of Remembering, Understanding, and Analyzing. Using descriptive and experimental method of research, it involved 99 Grade 8 students of Calamba City Science Integrated School which is 100% of the population under the online learning modality, School Year 2020 – 2021. A 50-item teacher-made test, validated by experts was utilized for the pre-test and post-test to find out the significant difference in students' academic performance. Meanwhile, a 25-item survey questionnaire, also validated by experts, elicit the respondents' perception on game-based learning in Araling Panlipunan. Furthermore, an original digital game was created exclusively for this study wherein the content involved were the topics in Araling Panlipunan 8. Using the mean and standard deviation, the study described the profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, and time spent in playing digital games, and the students' pre-test and post-test scores. In addition, Pearson's correlation coefficient was utilized to determine the significant relationship between the perception of students in game-based learning and academic performance of students in terms of remembering, understanding, and analyzing skills. Meanwhile, it was concluded that the first null hypothesis is rejected – there is a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of the respondents. Then, the second null hypothesis is accepted - there was no significant relationship between game-based learning and academic performance of students. Finally, it can be inferred that Araling Panlipunan teachers may create and incorporate digital games not only as a form of motivation, but as well as a form of presenting lectures and a form of assessment.

Keywords: (a) education, Araling Panlipunan 8, (b) digital game-based learning, rules, immersive, enjoyment, multimedia technology, challenge & competition, remembering, understanding, analyzing, (c) quantitative, descriptive, experimental, correlational, (d) Philippines